

Undergraduate Research in a Fully Online Engineering Program: Effects on Retention, Persistence, Performance, STEM Attitudes and Identity Project Outcomes Report

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The *Undergraduate Research in a Fully Online Engineering Program: Effects on Retention, Persistence, Performance, STEM Attitudes and Identity* project (Award no. 2021221) was focused on enhance undergraduate research opportunities for students enrolled in a fully online engineering program. Over a three-year period, the project progressed through the development, launch, and awareness-building phases, implementing initiatives such as the Research Scholar Program, Undergraduate Research Workshops, and support for active undergraduate researchers, while building partnerships with collaborative student resources, such as the COMPASS Research Mentoring Program and the VECTOR Virtual Communication Lab.

Intellectual Merit

The experiences, observations, and outcomes from this work serve to provide insights into the dynamics of program persistence and retention, academic performance, STEM identity and attitudes, transferable skills, and the transferability of the framework to other programs. The study featured an exploration of the impact Distance Research framework has on student persistence and retention, as the first and second objectives. While initially proposed solely for online engineering students, the scope was widened to include technical STEM student participants due to challenges associated with recruitment of the original population. Qualitative data collected from research mentees' interviews provided insights into academic milestone self-efficacy. Findings also suggested positive influences on STEM student confidence in advanced coursework. Data from mentee interviews indicated positive impacts on self-efficacy related to degree completion. However, a low sample size limited subgroup analysis.

The third objective aimed to evaluate the framework's impact on the academic performance of online engineering students. Although recruitment challenges persisted, student performance in a three-credit independent study course created for the program exhibited student proficiency in research-related skills and successful achievement of learning objectives.

Objective four connected to understanding how the framework potentially affected STEM identity and attitudes. Preliminary findings suggested that engaging in research positively influenced STEM identity, even before formal participation. Despite a low response rate in surveys, research mentee interviews highlighted positive impacts on students' perceptions of STEM concepts and themselves as STEM individuals.

The project also included an investigation of how the framework potentially affected transferable skills for online engineering and technical STEM students. Although the specific impact on B.S. Engineering Technology students was not measured, research

mentee interviews indicated the development of key transferable skills, such as information literacy, critical thinking, communication, and time management.

The final objective was focused on examining the transferability of the framework to other online degree programs. Challenges in shifting focus solely to B.S. Engineering Technology students hindered the development of a transferability plan. However, engagement of non-BSET/ technical STEM students suggested potential applicability to other STEM-related programs.

Broader Impacts

The key intent of this project was to leverage acquired knowledge to create and examine a comprehensive framework for supporting undergraduate research in online engineering degrees, adaptable for implementation by various institutions. Despite encountering challenges in recruiting the intended student demographic, a pivot to an expanded technical STEM population led to successful extraction of key findings. The subsequent insights were made publicly accessible through a series of external dissemination products, emphasizing actions most conducive to enhancing student learning, persistence, retention, and perspectives.

The broader impacts of the project were evident in several key outcomes. First, seven students were awarded stipends for their research involvement, highlighting the project's success in fostering student participation and commitment. The mentee interview study revealed that engagement in research mentorship resulted in disciplinary learning gains, development of transferable skills, and an enhanced sense of belonging, with some participants reporting increased persistence and retention in STEM fields. Notably, one student experienced a redirected career path as a significant outcome of their research mentorship experience. Another student completed the Undergraduate Research Certificate, reflecting a transformative perspective on research. Furthermore, students successfully disseminated their research through conferences, journals, and recognition at the Worldwide campus, emphasizing the significance of their work and contributing to the broader impact of the project on the academic community.

Conclusion

The Research Scholars program, initially developed for a single engineering program, extended its benefits to the entire Worldwide campus, reaching beyond the intended population. Through advertising, 3,563 students were reached. As of September 2023, the Canvas page for the Research Scholars program has 211 student members, while the partnered COMPASS Research Mentoring Program supported 34 research mentees (30 undergraduates, 4 graduate students) between August 2021 and September 2023. Although initially focused on establishing a framework within a specific discipline, broad interest among students from various disciplines was discovered in the research opportunities and support structure provided, encompassing mentoring and workshops. The outcomes of the initiative have not only altered expectations for distance students at the examined institution but have also led to an aspiration to challenge stereotypes about online education across different institutions.